

THE USE OF MILITARY TERMS IN RUSSIAN CLASSES

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Annotation: The article presents the problem of introducing military-professional lexical material in the framework of studying Russian as a foreign language in a military university. The methods of semanticization are analyzed and the choice of the most effective method of semanticization is justified when introducing military-professional vocabulary. The specifics of the educational institution determined the choice of the lexical thematic group on which the authors' attention is focused, namely, military-professional vocabulary. The choice of the material is also justified by the practical side of training, since the use of it by students is a necessary condition for their daily professional duties. The article discusses the ways of introducing military-professional and drill vocabulary in the framework of the preparatory course, talks about possible ways to control the assimilation of lexical material, provides methodological recommendations based on specific pedagogical experience.

Keywords: *vocabulary, semantics, Russian as a foreign language, military personnel, military-professional vocabulary, method, method.*

Recently, there has been a tendency to increase interest on the part of foreign countries in obtaining Russian military special education. In this regard, the number of servicemen from near and far abroad countries seeking to study at Russian military universities of various profiles is growing. Such trainees include not only cadets receiving higher education, but also officers undergoing refresher courses or professional retraining. Russian military universities for foreign military personnel are mainly taught in Russian, which necessitates the study of the Russian language in the framework of preparatory courses.

At the initial stage of training, difficulties may arise when foreign servicemen perform their daily duties, since Russian officers and cadets do not always speak the foreign language spoken by a newly arrived foreign cadet or an officer of the retraining group. Such difficulties are most often associated with the use of professional, drill vocabulary, the implementation of the disciplinary statute prescribing the use of fixed formulas of greeting / response / farewell. The removal of the language barrier is facilitated by the introduction of specific military drill vocabulary already at the initial stages of RCT training. In our opinion, the expediency of introducing professional lexical units mainly of a

combat and disciplinary nature is due to the need to solve a number of communicative problems that arise in the first days of service. For example, after studying the Russian alphabet and in the process of introducing polysyllabic words, foreign servicemen get acquainted with the vocabulary denoting a military rank or position, an performed duty: colonel, major, captain, teacher, officer, cadet, commander, duty officer. It is also mandatory for a military university to use the word comrade in connection with all the listed lexemes.

As part of the development of the elementary level of proficiency in Russian as a foreign language at the preparatory department, cadets are acquainted with some verb forms (get up, let me report, let me address, I wish you good health), since the report of the duty officer at the beginning and at the end of the lesson is an obligatory element. When getting acquainted with the new vocabulary of a particular thematic group, introduced into the active vocabulary, it is necessary to take into account the key points of the process of forming word use skills. Starting acquaintance with the meaning and form of the word, i.e. from the grammatical and semantic component, it is important to move on to the syntactic aspect, in particular, to the use of the word in the flow of speech, its connection with the right and left context of the sentence, which, in turn, is the inclusion of the studied vocabulary in the communication process, and hence the formation of communicative competence.

The formation of a lexical skill occurs through the formation of various connections in the process of learning a language. First of all, these are denotative, situational, symbolic, semantic and background connections of lexical units. The semantics of the new vocabulary is carried out through the actualization of all types of connections or some of them. When introducing military-professional vocabulary, denotative, situational or semantic connection of lexical units is most often used. Thus, semantics, or rather, the choice of the method of semantics in each case will depend on the fixed form of the word being entered, on the syntactic model, on the situation of use and the presence/absence of analogues in another language. But in any case, it is necessary to organize the presented lexical material in such a way as to teach listeners to pronounce a word, identify it in the flow of speech, understand the meaning, write (if necessary), and also include it in the communication process.

The military vocabulary belongs to the group of active vocabulary in the field of military-professional relations, therefore, the need for the formation of paradigmatic, syntactic and associative links when teaching Russian as a foreign language is obvious. To do this, it is important to methodically choose the right

way to introduce a new word into the active vocabulary of students. From the point of view of the methodology, it is important to take into account the stage of training (initial, basic, advanced level), the level of language proficiency, the time allotted for activating new vocabulary, the technical security of the educational process, pay attention to the age of the student (cadet / officer) and the level of language abilities.

Thus, teaching Russian as a foreign language in a military university, the teacher of the preparatory department is faced with the task of choosing the most rational and effective ways of working with lexical material in order to prepare foreign servicemen for the subsequent profession, as well as the qualitative performance of military duties.

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